

THE
TELEMIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The spider family Telemidae currently contains 14 genera and 97 species. In South Africa only one genus *Cangoderces* is known from two species. They are very rare spiders and less than 10 specimens have been collected. Two specimens of *Cangoderces globosa* Wang, Li & Haddad, 2018 have been collected from litter in Mpumalanga. The status of the species remains obscure and some more sampling is needed to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient. *Cangoderces lewisi* Harington 1951 is known from a few specimens and due to the species having a small restricted distribution range and being recorded from only one locality it is therefore listed as Critically Rare.

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FAMILY TELEMIDAE Fage 1913

The spider family Telemidae currently contains 14 genera and 97 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) that are distributed in tropical Africa, East and South-East Asia, and North and Central America.

COMMON NAME: Long-legged Cave Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Cangoderces lewisi* Harington, 1951

MORPHOLOGY: Size: < 2 mm. Colour: brown, usually with purplish blue sheen. Carapace: slightly wider than long; sternum fused to labium or with T-shaped suture; cheliceral margin without lamina; both cheliceral furrows with teeth; labium rebordered; eyes: six eyes or none; usually in three diads; legs: three claws; legs long and slender with few spines; tarsi without trichobothria; tibia with mid-dorsal integumental glands opening onto cuticular plates; abdomen: slightly elongated, with sclerotized zigzag ridge above pedicel, more distinct in males; genitalia: haplogyne; female genitalia with a single large spermatheca; male palp with a ribbon-like spermatophore; bulb simple, attached basally to cymbium.

LIFESTYLE: Little is known about the behaviour of telemids. Most genera are cavernicolous or live in rock beds or are found in litter in forests. Emerit (1981, 1984) and Emerit & Juberthie (1983) reported on the discovery of mid dorsal tibial integumentary glands in the Telemidae. These glands, which may produce a repugnatorial secretion, are present on the tibia of all legs in both males and females and open onto cuticular plates.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Two species known from South Africa described by Harington (1951) and Wang, Li & Haddad (2018)

Telemidae a: *Cangoderces* sp. male, lateral view; b: body, dorsal view, showing eye pattern and pedicel; c: tarsus with claws; d: spinnerets, ventral view; e: male palp, lateral view; f: female genitalia. (c, d, f after Harington, 1951; e after Brignoli, 1978b.)

GENUS *CANGODERCES* Harington, 1951

The genus *Cangoderces* was erected by Harington (1951) based on seven females of the type species, *C. lewisi*, collected in the Cango Caves in south-western South Africa, and placed in the Leptonetidae: Ochyroceratinae. Subsequently, Machado (1956) transferred the genus to Telemidae and Brignoli (1978) described the male of *C. lewisi* for the first time.

COMMON NAME: Cangoderces Long-legged cave spiders

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: <2 mm. Colour: brown, usually with purplish blue sheen. Carapace: slightly wider than long; sternum: fused to labium or with T-shaped suture; eyes: six eyes in three diads; chelicerae: inner cheliceral margin without lamina; both cheliceral furrows toothed; mouthparts with labium rebordered. Abdomen slightly elongated, with sclerotized zigzag ridge above pedicel, more distinct in males; spinnerets: large rhomboidal colulus; anterior spinnerets two-segmented; booklungs absent; two pairs of tracheae, posterior pair near middle. Legs: three claws; long and slender with few spines; tarsi without trichobothria. Genitalia haplogyne; female genitalia with a single large spermathecal.

LIFESTYLE: In South Africa *Cangoderces lewisi* was collected from the Cango Caves, South Africa, while *C. globosa* was found in leaf litter in Afromontane forest.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The genus *Cangoderces* is known from six African species of which two are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2021).

Cangoderces sp. male Photo Charles Haddad

Cangoderces lewisi male after Harington (1951)

Chelicerae male after Wang et al. (2018)

Cangoderces globosa Wang, Li & Haddad, 2018

COMMON NAME: Telemid Litter Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Mpumalanga endemic described by Wang et al. (2018) from the type locality Sabie (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1556 m a.s.l.). The species is known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Mpumalanga*: Sabie, Mountain Gorge on Road 37 (-25.16917, 30.76387).

LIFESTYLE: Sampled while sifting leaf litter in Afromontane forest.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Cangoderces globosa female and male after Wang et al. (2018)

Cangoderces lewisi Harington, 1951

COMMON NAME: Cango Cave Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: Critically Rare

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Harington (1951) from the type locality the Cango Caves in Oudtshoorn (EOO=<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 357 ma.s.l.). The species is known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range. Due to the species having a small restricted distribution range and being recorded from only one locality it is therefore listed as Critically Rare.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Cango Caves, Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21).

LIFESTYLE: *Cangoderces lewisi* was collected from the Cango Caves, South Africa, about 700 m from the entrance, where individuals were found in space webs spun in small crevices in the rock wall about 30-40 cm above the footpath in the total dark zone of the cave (Harington, 1951, Dippenaar-Schoeman, Myburgh 2009).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range. The species is endangered because of the commercial activities in the cave.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from both sexes.

Male palp after Brignoli (1978)

Cangoderces lewisi female after Harington (1951)

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